

RESEARCH, INSIGHTS, AND IDEAS

The Knowledge Series

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Research Bulletin Volume (1)

Dedicated to the People of Myanmar

The Knowledge Series research bulletin highlights the primary roles and responsibilities of key institutions—government, political parties, military, and police force—that shape the direction of a nation. This bulletin also underscores the ethical responsibilities these institutions must uphold in serving the people.

We hope that readers, whether familiar with these concepts or not, gain valuable insights and apply this knowledge to contribute to the nation's development. By doing so, each individual can play a meaningful role in building the future as responsible citizens.

The Knowledge Series research bulletin is available in both Burmese and English, ensuring accessibility for a wider audience.

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18 September 2024

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Research Bulletin Volume (1)

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Maung Ba Oo

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Chapter 1: GOVERNMENT

A. What is the purpose of a government in a country? What are its roles?

The purpose of a government in a country is to organize and regulate society, ensuring order, security, and the well-being of its citizens. Governments are necessary because they provide the structure within which a society can function effectively, resolving conflicts, enforcing laws, and delivering public services. Without a government, a society might struggle with chaos, violence, and an inability to meet the collective needs of its people.

Roles of a Government

1. **Law and Order:** Governments create and enforce laws to maintain social order, protect citizens, and ensure justice. This includes criminal laws, civil laws, and regulations that guide economic and social interactions.
2. **Security and Defense:** Protecting a country from external threats is a fundamental role of the government. This involves maintaining armed forces, intelligence services, and other security agencies to safeguard the nation's sovereignty.
3. **Economic Management:** Governments regulate economic activities to ensure stable growth, manage inflation, reduce unemployment, and promote

economic prosperity. This can involve monetary policy, taxation, trade regulations, and fiscal policy.

4. **Provision of Public Services:** Governments provide essential services that individuals and private entities may not adequately supply, such as education, healthcare, transportation infrastructure, sanitation, and utilities.
5. **Social Welfare:** Governments often play a role in reducing inequality and providing support for the vulnerable through welfare programs, unemployment benefits, healthcare, and housing assistance.
6. **Environmental Protection:** Governments establish and enforce environmental regulations to protect natural resources, ensure sustainable development, and address issues like pollution and climate change.
7. **Diplomacy and International Relations:** Governments engage in diplomacy to manage relationships with other countries, negotiate treaties, and address global challenges such as trade, security, and climate change.
8. **Representation and Advocacy:** In democratic systems, governments represent the interests and will of the people. This involves creating policies that reflect public opinion, protecting human rights, and ensuring freedom and democracy.

B. Is a government necessary in a country?

A government is necessary in a country for several reasons:

- **Maintaining Order:** Without a governing body to enforce laws and mediate disputes, society could

descend into chaos, with conflicts resolved through violence rather than legal means.

- **Providing Services:** Essential services like healthcare, education, infrastructure, and security are often beyond the capacity of private entities to provide equitably, requiring government intervention.
- **Economic Stability:** Governments help stabilize the economy by managing inflation, unemployment, and ensuring a fair distribution of resources through taxation and social policies.
- **Protecting Rights and Freedoms:** Governments safeguard the rights and freedoms of individuals, ensuring that everyone is treated equally under the law and that human rights are protected.
- **Global Engagement:** In an interconnected world, governments play a crucial role in representing the country's interests internationally, addressing global challenges, and maintaining peace.

In summary, a government is essential for organizing society, providing public goods, ensuring justice, and protecting the rights and well-being of its citizens. Without it, the complexities of modern life and the collective needs of a society would be difficult, if not impossible, to manage effectively.

C. Are there any countries in the world without a government?

There is no country in the world that exists entirely without a government. A government, in some form, is essential for the functioning of any organized society, as it provides structure,

enforces laws, and manages resources. However, there have been instances where countries have experienced periods of government collapse, severe instability, or a lack of effective central authority.

Examples of Countries with Governmental Collapse or Instability:

1. **Somalia (1991-2012):** For over two decades, Somalia was often cited as a "failed state" due to the collapse of its central government in 1991 after the overthrow of President Siad Barre. The country descended into chaos, with various warlords and militant groups controlling different regions. There was no effective national government during this time, and the country was marked by lawlessness, violence, and humanitarian crises. However, efforts to restore a central government began in the 2000s, and by 2012, Somalia had established a new federal government.
2. **Libya (post-2011):** After the fall of Muammar Gaddafi in 2011, Libya has struggled with severe instability and fragmentation. Multiple factions, including rival governments, militias, and tribal groups, have controlled different parts of the country, leading to a lack of a unified and effective central government. Despite attempts to form a unified government, Libya has continued to experience significant political and social unrest.

Stateless Societies and Autonomous Regions:

While there is no country without a government, there are some regions or communities within countries that operate with a high degree of autonomy or have alternative governance structures:

- **Rojava (Syrian Kurdistan):** The autonomous region of Rojava in northeastern Syria has developed a unique system of governance known as "democratic confederalism," which emphasizes direct democracy, gender equality, and local self-governance. While not entirely without a government, Rojava operates with a decentralized form of governance different from traditional state structures.
- **Anarchist Communities:** Some small communities or regions, particularly in historical contexts, have attempted to operate without a formal government, instead relying on anarchist principles of self-organization and mutual aid. These experiments are often short-lived and typically occur within the context of larger states.

Conclusion:

While there may be regions or historical periods where central governments have collapsed or where alternative forms of governance have been attempted, every recognized country today has some form of government, even if it is weak, ineffective, or fragmented. The existence of a government, in some capacity, is essential for the stability, security, and organization of any society.

Chapter 2: POLITICAL PARTIES

A. What is the purpose of a political party in a country? What are its roles?

The purpose of a political party in a country is to organize individuals who share similar political beliefs, values, and goals into a collective group that seeks to influence government policy, represent citizens' interests, and participate in the democratic process. Political parties are essential in a democracy as they provide a structured way for citizens to express their political preferences, offer choices during elections, and help form and implement public policy.

Roles of a Political Party

1. **Representation of Interests:** Political parties represent the diverse interests, opinions, and demands of different segments of society. By aggregating these interests, they help ensure that various groups have a voice in the political process.
2. **Political Participation:** Parties encourage citizens to participate in politics by mobilizing voters, organizing campaigns, and educating the public about issues and candidates. They play a key role in engaging the electorate and promoting civic involvement.
3. **Policy Formulation:** Political parties develop policy platforms that outline their positions on key issues. These platforms guide their legislative agendas and

provide voters with clear choices about the direction they want the country to take.

4. **Government Formation:** In democratic systems, the party or coalition with the most support usually forms the government. Political parties nominate candidates for public office, contest elections, and, if successful, assume positions of power to implement their policies.
5. **Accountability:** Parties in power are held accountable by opposition parties and the electorate. This ensures that the government remains responsive to the needs of the people and operates transparently. The opposition plays a crucial role in scrutinizing government actions and offering alternative policies.
6. **Political Stability:** Political parties contribute to the stability of the political system by providing structured and predictable competition for power. They help manage conflict within society by channeling it into peaceful and democratic processes.
7. **Leadership Development:** Parties are a training ground for political leaders. They provide opportunities for individuals to develop their skills, gain experience, and rise through the ranks to assume leadership roles within the party and the government.
8. **Policy Implementation:** When in government, political parties are responsible for implementing their policy platforms. They guide the legislative and executive branches in passing laws, creating regulations, and administering programs that reflect their political agenda.
9. **Promoting Ideology:** Political parties promote specific ideologies and principles, such as

conservatism, liberalism, socialism, or environmentalism. By doing so, they shape the political culture and public discourse within the country.

10. **Facilitating Cooperation:** In multi-party systems, political parties often need to form coalitions to govern. This encourages cooperation and compromise, leading to more balanced and representative policymaking.

B. Is a Political Party Necessary?

Political parties are generally considered necessary in a country, particularly in democratic systems, for several reasons:

- **Organizing the Electorate:** Political parties organize and simplify the complex political landscape, making it easier for voters to understand where candidates stand on issues and make informed choices during elections.
- **Facilitating Governance:** Political parties provide a framework for forming governments and ensuring continuity and coherence in policymaking. They help ensure that governments are able to function effectively by providing leadership and policy direction.
- **Ensuring Representation:** Political parties ensure that various segments of society are represented in the political process, helping to prevent any single group from dominating the political agenda.
- **Promoting Accountability:** By competing in elections, political parties hold each other

accountable, ensuring that governments do not abuse power and that they remain responsive to the needs and demands of the electorate.

- **Enhancing Political Stability:** Political parties contribute to political stability by providing structured competition for power, reducing the likelihood of conflict and unrest.

In summary, political parties play a crucial role in organizing political life, representing the interests of citizens, and ensuring the smooth functioning of democratic governance. While the nature and importance of political parties can vary depending on the political system, they are generally seen as essential for the effective operation of democracy and the representation of diverse viewpoints within a society.

C. Are there any countries in the world without a political party?

There are a few countries in the world that either do not have political parties or have a single dominant party system where no other political parties exist or function effectively. These countries typically operate under different forms of government, such as absolute monarchies or other non-democratic regimes, where political pluralism is not practiced.

Examples of Countries Without Political Parties

1. Saudi Arabia:

- **Details:** Saudi Arabia is an absolute monarchy where political parties are not allowed. The country is governed by the royal family, with the King holding significant power. There are no

formal political parties, and political activities are strictly controlled. Governance is carried out through the royal family and appointed officials.

- **Government Structure:** The King, along with a council of ministers and advisors, makes decisions. The Shura Council, an advisory body, provides advice on governance, but it has no legislative power.

2. Oman:

- **Details:** Oman is another absolute monarchy where political parties are not permitted. The Sultan of Oman has significant authority, and there is no formal political party system. The country is governed by the Sultan and his appointed ministers.
- **Government Structure:** Oman has a Consultative Assembly (Majlis al-Shura) and a State Council (Majlis al-Dawla), which provide advice to the Sultan, but they do not function as political parties and have limited influence on the decision-making process.

3. Qatar:

- **Details:** Qatar is an absolute monarchy where political parties are banned. The Emir of Qatar has broad powers, and there is no political party system. The country is governed by the Emir and a council of ministers.
- **Government Structure:** Qatar has a Shura Council that provides consultation on governance issues, but like in Oman, it does not have legislative power, and political parties are absent.

4. United Arab Emirates (UAE):

- **Details:** The UAE is a federation of seven emirates, each governed by its own monarch. Political parties are not allowed, and the country is ruled by the emirate's leaders. The UAE operates without a formal political party system.
- **Government Structure:** The Federal Supreme Council, consisting of the seven emirate rulers, is the highest governing body. The President and Prime Minister are chosen from among the rulers.

5. Brunei:

- **Details:** Brunei is an absolute monarchy where political parties are not permitted. The Sultan of Brunei has absolute power, and the country is governed without political parties.
- **Government Structure:** The Sultan governs with the assistance of appointed ministers, and there is no political party system. Brunei has a Legislative Council, but it functions primarily as an advisory body.

Reasons for Lack of Political Parties

- **Absolute Monarchy:** In absolute monarchies, the ruling monarch holds significant power and typically does not allow the formation of political parties that could challenge their authority.
- **Controlled Political Environment:** In some countries, the political environment is tightly controlled by the ruling elite or royal family, and political pluralism is not permitted.

- **Cultural and Historical Factors:** In some cases, the absence of political parties is rooted in the country's historical and cultural context, where tribal or familial structures play a more significant role in governance than formal political parties.

Conclusion

While most countries around the world have political parties as part of their governance structures, a few, particularly in the Middle East and Southeast Asia, operate without them. These countries are typically absolute monarchies or have highly centralized forms of governance where political parties are either banned or do not play a role in the political process.

Chapter 3: MILITARY

A. What is the purpose of a military in a country? What are its roles?

The purpose of a military in a country is to protect and defend the nation's sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national interests. The military serves as a critical component of a country's security apparatus, ensuring that it can respond effectively to external threats, conflicts, and emergencies. The existence of a military is often seen as necessary to maintain national security, deter aggression, and provide stability.

Roles of a Military

1. **Defense of the Nation:** The primary role of the military is to defend the country against external threats, such as invasions, attacks, or aggression from other states or groups. This involves maintaining armed forces capable of protecting the nation's borders, airspace, and maritime territories.
2. **Deterrence:** A strong military acts as a deterrent to potential aggressors. The mere existence of a capable military force can discourage other countries or groups from attempting to attack or undermine the nation, as they recognize the potential consequences.
3. **National Security:** Beyond defending against traditional military threats, the military plays a role in maintaining national security by addressing non-traditional threats such as terrorism, cyberattacks,

and natural disasters. This can involve specialized units within the military that focus on these areas.

4. **Support in Times of Crisis:** The military often assists in times of national crisis, such as natural disasters, pandemics, or internal conflicts. This includes providing logistical support, search and rescue operations, medical assistance, and maintaining order when civilian institutions are overwhelmed.
5. **Peacekeeping and Humanitarian Missions:** Many countries contribute military forces to international peacekeeping missions under the United Nations or other international organizations. These missions aim to maintain peace in conflict zones, protect civilians, and support humanitarian efforts.
6. **Protection of National Interests:** The military may be used to protect the country's national interests abroad, such as securing trade routes, protecting citizens overseas, and participating in alliances or coalitions that align with the country's strategic goals.
7. **Training and Development:** The military also serves as a training ground for leadership, discipline, and technical skills. Military service can instill values such as duty, honor, and patriotism, which contribute to national unity and civic responsibility.
8. **Emergency Response and Civil Support:** In addition to traditional defense roles, the military often provides support to civilian authorities during emergencies. This can include disaster relief, responding to civil unrest, and assisting in public health crises.

B. Is a military necessary in a country?

A military is generally considered necessary in a country for several reasons:

- **National Defense:** Without a military, a country may be vulnerable to external threats, invasions, or aggression. A military is essential for defending national sovereignty and ensuring the safety of citizens.
- **Deterrence:** A capable military acts as a deterrent to potential aggressors. The knowledge that a country can defend itself can prevent conflicts from arising in the first place.
- **Stability and Order:** The military contributes to the overall stability of the nation by providing security, especially in times of internal unrest or crisis.
- **International Engagement:** Participation in international military coalitions, peacekeeping, and humanitarian missions can enhance a country's standing on the global stage and help promote peace and security internationally.
- **National Pride and Unity:** The military often serves as a symbol of national pride and unity, helping to foster a sense of identity and belonging among citizens.

In summary, the military plays a vital role in protecting a country's sovereignty, ensuring national security, and providing stability in times of crisis. While the specific role and size of the military can vary depending on a country's

circumstances, its existence is generally seen as necessary to safeguard the nation and its interests.

C. Are there any countries in the world without a military or an army?

There are several countries in the world that do not have a standing military or army. These countries have chosen to maintain national security without a conventional military force, often relying on alternative security arrangements such as police forces, coast guards, or mutual defense treaties with other nations.

Examples of Countries Without a Military

1. Costa Rica:

- **Reason:** Costa Rica abolished its military in 1949 after a civil war. The decision was made to redirect military spending towards education, healthcare, and environmental protection. Costa Rica is often cited as an example of a peaceful country that has maintained stability without a military.
- **Security:** Costa Rica relies on its police force and has mutual defense agreements, primarily with the United States and other neighboring countries.

2. Iceland:

- **Reason:** Iceland does not have a standing military due to its peaceful history and geographical isolation. The country focuses on other forms of national defense and security.

- **Security:** Iceland is a member of NATO and relies on the alliance, particularly the United States, for defense. It maintains a small coast guard for maritime security and has agreements with other NATO countries for military protection.

3. Panama:

- **Reason:** Panama abolished its military in 1990 following the U.S. invasion that overthrew dictator Manuel Noriega. The decision was part of a broader effort to demilitarize the country and focus on civilian rule.
- **Security:** Panama relies on its police force and the Panamanian Public Forces for internal security and has defense agreements with the United States for external threats.

4. Liechtenstein:

- **Reason:** Liechtenstein disbanded its military in 1868 due to the high cost of maintaining it. The country decided to remain neutral in conflicts and focus on diplomacy and economic development.
- **Security:** Liechtenstein relies on Switzerland for military defense, as the two countries have a close relationship. It maintains a police force for internal security.

5. Vatican City:

- **Reason:** Vatican City, as the smallest independent state in the world, does not have a military. Its security is provided by the Swiss

Guard, a small force responsible for protecting the Pope and the Vatican.

- **Security:** The Vatican relies on Italy for broader security and defense. The Swiss Guard acts as both a ceremonial and protective force within the Vatican.

6. Japan

Reason: After World War II, Japan was left without a military for about seven years, relying on the United States for protection. In 1954, Japan established the Japan Self-Defense Forces (JSDF). Today, JSDF have a strictly defensive role, which includes: defense against external threats, disaster relief, and international peacekeeping.

Security: Japan's defense is a shared responsibility between JSDF and the United States. The JSDF handles Japan's primary defense against external threats, especially in territorial waters and airspace. The United States is committed to defending Japan under the U.S.-Japan Security Treaty. The U.S. provides additional military capabilities, including nuclear deterrence, which Japan does not have.

Japanese post-war economic miracle: Japan entered a period of rapid economic growth and modernization, often referred to as the Japanese post-war economic miracle, although Japan's defense policy remained constrained by its constitution, relying on the United States for much of its external security.

Reasons for Not Having a Military

- **Geopolitical Stability:** Some countries are located in regions where the threat of external aggression is low, allowing them to prioritize other areas over military spending.
- **Economic Considerations:** Maintaining a military is expensive, and some countries prefer to allocate resources to social services, infrastructure, and economic development.
- **Historical Decisions:** In some cases, countries have abolished their military after experiencing conflict or dictatorship, choosing to focus on peace and civilian governance.
- **International Agreements:** Some countries rely on defense agreements with more powerful nations or international organizations, such as the United States, NATO, for their security needs.

Conclusion

While most countries in the world maintain a military for defense and security, a few have chosen to exist without one. These countries often rely on alternative security arrangements, such as police forces, coast guards, and international defense agreements, to maintain their sovereignty and protect their citizens.

Chapter 4: POLICE FORCE

A. What is the purpose of a police force in a country? What are its roles?

The purpose of a police force in a country is to maintain law and order, protect citizens, prevent and investigate crimes, and uphold justice. The police are essential in enforcing the laws of the country, ensuring the safety and security of individuals and communities, and maintaining public order. They act as the primary agency responsible for internal security and play a crucial role in the justice system.

Roles of a Police Force

1. **Law Enforcement:** The primary role of the police is to enforce the laws of the country. This includes arresting individuals who break the law, issuing fines, and ensuring that legal statutes are followed by all members of society.
2. **Crime Prevention:** Police work to prevent crime through patrolling, community engagement, intelligence gathering, and visible presence in high-risk areas. They aim to deter criminal activity before it occurs by making potential offenders aware that the area is being monitored.
3. **Investigation of Crimes:** When crimes do occur, the police are responsible for investigating them. This includes collecting evidence, interviewing witnesses,

and working with other agencies to solve cases and bring offenders to justice.

4. **Protection of Citizens and Property:** Police protect individuals and their property from harm. This involves responding to emergencies, providing security at public events, and offering assistance in situations where people are in danger.
5. **Maintaining Public Order:** The police are tasked with maintaining order in public spaces, ensuring that public gatherings, protests, and other events occur peacefully. They manage crowds, control traffic, and intervene when necessary to prevent disturbances.
6. **Community Policing:** Modern police forces often engage in community policing, which involves building relationships with community members to understand their concerns, reduce fear of crime, and collaborate on public safety efforts.
7. **Support During Emergencies:** Police often serve as first responders during emergencies such as natural disasters, accidents, or terrorist attacks. They coordinate with other emergency services, provide first aid, and help manage crisis situations.
8. **Enforcement of Traffic Laws:** Police ensure road safety by enforcing traffic laws, managing traffic flow, and investigating accidents. They aim to reduce road accidents and promote safe driving behaviors.
9. **Judicial Support:** The police assist the judiciary by providing evidence, securing crime scenes, and ensuring that legal processes are followed during investigations and trials.

10. **Counterterrorism:** In many countries, the police are involved in counterterrorism efforts, working to prevent and respond to terrorist activities through intelligence gathering, surveillance, and specialized units.

B. Is a police force necessary?

A police force is necessary in a country for several reasons:

- **Maintaining Law and Order:** Without a police force, a country would struggle to maintain law and order, leading to increased crime, chaos, and insecurity. Police ensure that laws are enforced and that people can live in a safe and orderly society.
- **Crime Prevention:** The presence of a police force deters criminal activity and helps to prevent crimes before they occur. A society without police would be more vulnerable to crime and violence.
- **Public Safety:** Police play a crucial role in protecting the public from harm, whether through responding to emergencies, investigating crimes, or maintaining order in public spaces.
- **Justice System Support:** The police are integral to the functioning of the justice system. They gather evidence, arrest offenders, and support the prosecution of criminals, ensuring that justice is served.
- **Community Trust and Stability:** Through community policing and engagement, police help build trust between law enforcement and the public, contributing to social stability and cooperation.

In summary, a police force is essential for enforcing laws, maintaining public order, and protecting citizens and property. It plays a critical role in ensuring the safety and security of society, supporting the justice system, and preventing and responding to crime. Without a police force, a country would likely face significant challenges in maintaining peace, security, and the rule of law.

C. Are there any countries in the world without a police force?

No country in the world operates entirely without a police force. The police are a fundamental institution in maintaining law and order, ensuring public safety, enforcing laws, and protecting citizens' rights. However, there are some unique cases where countries have implemented alternative forms of law enforcement or have different structures that serve similar functions.

Unique Cases of Law Enforcement

1. Vatican City:

- **Details:** Vatican City, the smallest independent state in the world, does not have a traditional police force as seen in larger countries. However, it relies on the Swiss Guard for security and order within the Vatican. The Vatican also has a small corps of Vatican City State Police responsible for maintaining law and order, traffic control, and general security.
- **Alternative Structure:** The Swiss Guard, although primarily ceremonial, provides security for the Pope and the Vatican. The

Vatican City State Police handle typical law enforcement duties within the city-state.

2. Tuvalu:

- **Details:** Tuvalu, a small island nation in the Pacific Ocean, has a very small police force due to its size and low crime rate. The police force is not as extensive or formalized as those in larger countries, but it exists to maintain law and order.
- **Alternative Structure:** The police in Tuvalu are minimal, but they still perform the necessary functions of maintaining peace, enforcing laws, and providing basic security.

3. Nauru:

- **Details:** Similar to Tuvalu, Nauru is a small island nation with a very limited police presence. Due to its small population and geographic isolation, the demand for a large police force is low, but the country does maintain a police force to handle law enforcement.
- **Alternative Structure:** The police force in Nauru is small and focused on basic law enforcement and public safety.

In Summary, While every country has some form of law enforcement, the size, structure, and role of the police force can vary significantly depending on the country's size, population, and specific needs. Even in the smallest or most unique cases, a basic police presence or equivalent security force is essential for maintaining law and order. The absence of a formal police force would likely lead to significant

challenges in enforcing laws, protecting citizens, and ensuring public safety.

D. Control over Police Forces:

Ministry of Interior (or Home Affairs):

In most countries, the police force falls under the Ministry of Interior or Home Affairs, which is responsible for internal security and law enforcement.

State/Provincial Control:

In federal countries like the U.S., India, and Germany, police forces operate under state or regional control, though national authorities manage specialized or federal law enforcement agencies.

Shared Authority:

In countries like Japan, police forces have both local (prefectural) and national-level coordination.

Attorney General's Department:

Some countries have their police forces, particularly national or federal law enforcement, controlled or supervised by the Attorney General's Department or a similar legal authority. Examples include Australia, the United States, Sri Lanka, and New Zealand. In these countries, the Attorney General ensures that law enforcement operates within the legal framework and upholds national laws. This oversight helps balance law enforcement with the judiciary, ensuring police actions align with legal standards and constitutional principles.

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